

Contesting Increasing Trends of Non-Civic Attitudes in Pakistani Society

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Abstract

This article explores the contesting trends observed in contemporary society regarding the issue of non-civic sense. Non-civic sense refers to the lack of consideration and respect for public spaces, resources, and fellow citizens, leading to various problems and deteriorating the overall quality of life. In recent years, there has been a growing concern about the prevalence of non-civic sense and its impact on society. This abstract aims to highlight the contrasting perspectives, ongoing debates, and potential solutions surrounding this issue. The first section of this abstract examines the multiple dimensions of non-civic sense, including littering, vandalism, noise pollution, disregard for traffic rules, and other related behaviors. It delves into the underlying causes behind such behavior, ranging from societal norms and cultural factors to individual attitudes and lack of awareness. By identifying the various manifestations of non-civic sense, this section sets the foundation for understanding the contesting trends in society. The second section analyzes the conflicting viewpoints surrounding non-civic sense. On one hand, proponents argue that individual freedoms and personal choices should be prioritized over strict civic regulations. They believe that excessive enforcement might infringe upon individual rights and stifle creativity. On the other hand, critics emphasize the importance of collective responsibility and the need for stricter regulations to maintain order, cleanliness, and harmony in public spaces. This section presents the diverse perspectives on this issue, highlighting the ongoing debates and societal divisions. The final section explores potential solutions and interventions to address non-civic sense. It investigates the role of education, public awareness campaigns, community engagement, and policy changes in promoting a culture of civic responsibility. Furthermore, it examines the effectiveness of enforcement mechanisms, such as fines and penalties, in deterring non-civic behaviors. This section also acknowledges the challenges in implementing these solutions, including resistance to change, lack of resources, and the need for sustained efforts. In conclusion, this abstract, sheds light on the contesting trends in the society of non-civic sense. It underscores the importance of understanding the multidimensional nature of this issue and the diverse perspectives surrounding it. By examining the causes, contrasting viewpoints, and potential solutions, this abstract contributes to the ongoing dialogue aimed at fostering a more responsible and considerate society. Addressing non-civic sense requires a collective effort that encompasses education, awareness, community engagement, and well-designed policies to shape a more cohesive and harmonious social environment.

Keywords: Contesting increasing trends, Non-civic attitudes, Society, multidimensional, social environment

Introduction

Civic sense stands as the cornerstone of a vibrant democracy and a well-functioning society, exemplifying individuals' ability to empathize and act in harmony with their fellow citizens. It encompasses a range of qualities and habits that foster civically responsible behavior, from understanding civic duties towards the community and nation to valuing the common good above personal interests. Responsible citizens refrain from littering, spitting, and disrupting public spaces, creating an environment of cleanliness and respect. They uphold traffic rules, fulfill tax obligations, and respect public property, showcasing a deep sense of ownership and accountability to society, which leads us to being a "good citizen".

A good citizen, in the context of civic sense, embodies a profound commitment to upholding the principles of justice, fairness, and respect for the rights and well-being of others. They actively engage in civic affairs, participate responsibly in governance, and strive to contribute positively to the betterment of their community and nation. A good citizen exemplifies empathy, compassion, and a strong sense of social responsibility, serving as a role model for others to emulate in fostering a harmonious and thriving society.

Definition of Civic Education

Defining civic education reveals the complexities and contested nature of the concept, as it involves three dimensions: education about citizenship, education for citizenship, and education through citizenship. Cultivating responsible citizenship involves instilling a profound sense of duty towards the community and shared values. By empowering individuals through civic education and fostering genuine civic responsibility, societies can forge a path towards active and engaged citizenship. Embracing civic duty, empathy, and communal welfare can counteract the rising trends of non-civic attitudes, protecting the fabric of responsible citizenship in our society. The celebration of positive role models and civic education will illuminate the way towards a compassionate, inclusive, and thriving society, where citizens uplift each other, one civic gesture at a time.

Causes of Non-Civic Attitudes/Behavior in Pakistani Society: Unraveling the Underlying Threads of Disregard

Non-civic behavior refers to actions, attitudes, or behaviors exhibited by individuals that demonstrate a lack of concern, responsibility, or engagement towards the well-being of the broader community or society as a whole. It encompasses actions that go against the principles of responsible citizenship and societal norms. The prevalence of non-civic attitudes and behavior in Pakistani society is a complex phenomenon rooted in multifaceted dynamics. Non-civic behavior can manifest in various ways and is characterized by a disregard for public interests, public property, and the shared values that underpin a cohesive and harmonious society. As an expert observer, delving into the intricacies of this pervasive issue unveils a tapestry of causes that contribute to the erosion of responsible citizenship and communal cohesion. From societal norms to cultural factors, several

interwoven threads shape the fabric of non-civic attitudes in Pakistan.

Here's a brief explanation of each:

(a) Littering: Littering is a non-civic behaviour that can be related to a variety of society standards and cultural causes. The first piece examines how students' ideas of civic ideals are shaped by their immediate social circles, which include family and community. Individuals who see littering behaviour in their families or communities may normalise such behaviour since they view it to be acceptable or trivial. Furthermore, a lack of effective waste disposal infrastructure and public awareness efforts may contribute to apathy towards keeping public spaces clean.

(b) Vandalism: Vandalism, or the intentional destruction or defacement of public property, can be linked to society standards and cultural issues as well. The second part focuses on how historical and political developments in Pakistan have shaped civic sentiments. Individuals may consider public property as divorced from their personal interests as a result of the legacy of political instability and a sense of disempowerment. Furthermore, social hierarchies and power dynamics may motivate some to commit vandalism as a form of disobedience or to obtain attention within their peer groups.

(c) Noise Pollution: Noise pollution is frequently the outcome of uncivil behaviour that disregards the well-being and comfort of others in the community. The final article discusses how cultural conventions, such as tribal or clan affiliations, might influence civic behaviour. People in close-knit communities may be less sensitive to the influence of their loudness on others, assuming a level of familiarity that permits them to disregard fellow community members' rights to calm surroundings. Furthermore, a lack of awareness and education about the repercussions of noise pollution might exacerbate the problem.

(d) Disregard of Traffic Rules: A combination of reasons listed in the three paragraphs can impact contempt for traffic laws, a fundamental part of non-civic behaviour. The second piece focuses on the influence of political insecurity and authoritarian control on civic sentiments, which can emerge on the road as a disregard for traffic norms and regulations. Furthermore, societal norms that prioritise individual interests over communal well-being on the road may result in aggressive driving and a sense of entitlement on the road.

(e) Spitting in Public: Spitting in public places without regard for sanitation or hygiene, which can be offensive and unsightly.

(f) Encroachment of Public Spaces: Occupying or obstructing public areas such as footpaths, sidewalks, or parks, impeding the free movement of others

(g) Apathy towards Civic Issues: It is also can be termed as “lack of ownership towards Civic issues. Demonstrating indifference towards civic issues and public affairs, such as low voter turnout or lack of engagement in community initiatives. A feeling of detachment or lack of ownership towards public spaces and resources can contribute to a lack of responsibility and concern for their upkeep and maintenance.

(h) Non-Payment of Taxes: Failing to pay taxes on time, which undermines the collective resources necessary for public services and infrastructure development.

(j) Engaging in Public Nuisance: Participating in unruly or disruptive behavior that disturbs the peace and tranquility of public spaces.

(k) Increasing Individualism and Self-Centeredness: In societies that prioritize

individual interests over collective well-being, a lack of civic sense may emerge as people become more self-centered and less concerned about the impact of their actions on others. This individualistic attitude can be seen in many aspects of life, from the way people drive to how they dispose of trash. Another cause of lack of civic sense is the anonymity of modern life.

(l) Surrounded by strangers– In large cities, people are often surrounded by strangers and don't feel a sense of community or responsibility for their surroundings. This can lead to littering, graffiti, and other forms of vandalism.

(m) Increased Pace of Life- The third cause of lack of civic sense is the increased pace of life. With busy schedules and long work hours, people have less time to get involved in their communities or take care of their surroundings. This can lead to neglected public spaces and a general feeling of apathy towards community issues. All these causes contribute to a lack of civic sense and a decline in community spirit. To reverse this trend, it is important to encourage people to be more active citizens and take pride in their communities.

(n) Inadequate Education and Awareness: A lack of proper education and awareness about civic responsibilities and values can be a significant factor behind the absence of civic sense. When individuals are not adequately taught about the importance of community well-being and responsible citizenship, they may remain oblivious to the impact of their actions on society.

(p) Lack of Role Models: The absence of positive role models who exemplify civic-minded behavior can also influence individuals to neglect their civic duties. When influential figures fail to demonstrate responsible conduct, it can perpetuate a cycle of indifference and irresponsibility.

(q) Ingrained Cultural Norms: Certain cultural norms or traditions may inadvertently discourage civic-minded behavior. For instance, in some cultures, littering or spitting in public spaces may be deemed acceptable, leading to a disregard for maintaining cleanliness and order.

(r) Ineffective Enforcement of Laws and Regulations: Weak law enforcement and a lack of consequences for civic violations can contribute to a sense of impunity, wherein individuals feel they can disregard civic responsibilities without facing repercussions.

(s) Political Instability and Corruption: Societies grappling with political instability and corruption may experience a decline in civic sense. When citizens lose faith in their governance systems, they may feel less compelled to uphold civic values and responsibilities.

(t) Urbanization and Overpopulation: Rapid urbanization and overpopulation can strain public resources and infrastructure, leading to a sense of detachment and disconnection among individuals, which in turn impacts their civic sense.

(u) Negative Peer Influence: In some cases, negative peer influence or social pressure can discourage individuals from displaying responsible behavior. If non-civic attitudes are prevalent in certain social circles, individuals may conform to such behavior to fit in.

(v) Media Influence: The portrayal of irresponsible behavior in the media can also influence perceptions and norms, potentially contributing to a lack of civic sense among some segments of the population.

Individuals must develop civic responsibility and respect for others to contribute to a cleaner, safer, and more harmonious society. Fostering a culture of civic mindedness promotes

responsible citizenship, community engagement, and upholding shared values. Addressing the lack of civic sense requires education, awareness campaigns, positive role models, effective law enforcement, and collective effort. Untangling the complex web of causes behind non-civic attitudes in Pakistani society demands a multifaceted approach. By addressing these underlying factors through robust civic education, the promotion of positive role models, strengthening institutions, and fostering a culture of collective responsibility, we can strive towards a more engaged, empathetic, and harmonious society, where civic values form the bedrock of our shared progress.

Remedial measures to improve Civic attitudes/behaviour of Pakistani society

Civic sense is the basic awareness of the rights, duties, and responsibilities of a member of a community. It is the ability to see beyond one's own self-interest and work for the common good. Civic sense is developed through education, socialization and exposure to diverse people and cultures. It is important to improve civic sense to create more cohesive, sustainable, and just communities. Improving civic sense in Pakistani society requires a comprehensive approach involving various strategies. Here are some strategies that can be adopted to enhance civic sense:

- 1. Encourage critical thinking and questioning:** Teach children to question what they see and hear, and to think critically about the world around them. This will help them to be more informed citizens who are able to participate in civic life effectively.
- 2. Expose children to different cultures and perspectives:** It is important for children to understand that there are many different cultures and perspectives in the world. This will help them to be more tolerant and respectful of others, and to understand the importance of working together for the common good.
- 3. Promote active citizenship:** Encourage children to get involved in their communities, and to participate in civic life through volunteering, voting, etc. This will help them to develop a sense of responsibility for their community and its wellbeing.
- 4. Model good civic behavior:** As parents, teachers, etc., it is important that we model good civic behavior for children. This includes respecting the rights of others, obeying laws, and rules, being tolerant and respectful of differences, etc.
- 5. Comprehensive Civic Education:** A paramount step entails implementing comprehensive civic education programs across educational institutions. Infusing curricula with lessons on civic responsibilities, community welfare, and ethical citizenship from an early age nurtures a generation of socially conscious individual. These campaigns can be targeted at schools, community centers, and through media channels to raise awareness and promote positive behavior.
- 6. Community Engagement:** Encourage community participation in maintaining and improving public spaces. Organize community clean-up drives, beautification projects, and awareness events to foster a sense of ownership and pride among residents. Engage community leaders, local organizations, and volunteers in promoting positive behaviors and setting examples.
- 7. Public Signs and Messaging:** Install informative and visually appealing signs in public

spaces to educate and remind individuals about expected behavior. Use clear and concise messages that encourage responsible actions such as proper waste disposal, respect for public property, and consideration for others.

8. Peer Influence and Role Modeling: Promote positive peer pressure by highlighting and celebrating individuals or groups who demonstrate good civic sense. Encourage influential figures, such as celebrities or community leaders, to serve as role models by actively practicing and promoting civic-minded behaviors.

9. Enforcement and Penalties: Strengthen enforcement of existing regulations and by-laws related to public behavior. Increase the presence of law enforcement officers or security.

10. Strengthening the Legal Framework: Implement and enforce strict laws and regulations that promote civic behavior and punish offenders. This includes fines for littering, spitting in public places, and other forms of disruptive behavior.

11. Public Participation: Encourage active participation of citizens in public affairs, community events, and social initiatives. This can be achieved through volunteer programs, encouraging local community groups, and organizing cleanup campaigns.

12. Communication and Information: Utilize various communication channels, such as social media, to disseminate information about civic responsibilities, proper waste management, and the importance of maintaining clean and green public spaces.

13. Promote Ethical Leadership: Encourage ethical leadership at all levels of society, including politicians, officials, and community leaders. Leaders should set an example by following rules and regulations and promoting good civic behavior.

14. Infrastructure Development: Invest in the development of public infrastructure, including waste management systems, public toilets, and well-maintained public spaces. These improvements can help foster a sense of pride and responsibility among citizens.

15. Civic Engagement Programs: Foster a sense of ownership and responsibility among citizens through civic engagement programs, such as participatory budgeting, community clean-up drives, and neighborhood watch initiatives.

16. Encourage Social Norms: Promote social norms that prioritize cleanliness, respect for public property, and consideration for others. This can be achieved through media campaigns, cultural events, and public figures endorsing positive civic behavior.

17. Public-Private Partnerships: Establish partnerships between government bodies, civil society organizations, and private sector entities to collectively work towards improving civic sense and implementing effective solutions.

18. Continuous Evaluation and Improvement: Regularly assess the progress made in promoting civic sense and make necessary adjustments to the strategies as needed. This may involve conducting surveys, seeking feedback from citizens, and engaging in dialogue with stakeholders. A comprehensive and continuous strategy is essential in the aim of revitalising civic sentiments. Each corrective step interacts with others, resulting in a powerful synergy that raises Pakistani society's collective consciousness. By accepting these revolutionary measures, the country may chart a course towards a more educated, compassionate, and civically engaged people. Citizens stand shoulder to side in this path of social resurrection, symbolising the very essence of collective growth - a tribute to Pakistan's lasting ethos of responsible citizenship.

PROMOTING CIVIC SENSE: AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVE

In Islamic teachings, civic sense or civic responsibility is highly emphasized. Islam encourages its followers to be responsible members of society and to fulfill their duties towards their fellow human beings and the community as a whole. Here are some key points from an Islamic perspective regarding civic sense:

1. **Respect for Others:** Islam emphasizes the importance of treating others with respect and kindness. The Quran emphasizes the importance of kindness, respect, and consideration towards others in numerous verses. For example, in Surah Al-Hujaraat (49:11), it states,

لَا يَسْخَرُ قَوْمٌ مِنْ قَوْمٍ... وَلَا تَلْهَوْا أَنْفُسَكُمْ وَلَا تَنَابَرُوا بِاللِّقَابِ-

"O you who have believed, let not a people ridicule [another] people; perhaps they may be better than them; nor let women ridicule [other] women; perhaps they may be better than them."

In this verse, Allah addresses the believers, emphasizing the importance of mutual respect and forbearance within the society. The verse starts with the command, "O you who have believed," signifying that the guidance given here is directed towards the Muslim community. Allah urges the believers not to ridicule or mock one another". This directive extends to all people, regardless of their background, ethnicity, social status, or any other distinguishing characteristic. It underscores the significance of fostering a culture of inclusivity, tolerance, and empathy within the community. From the perspective of civic attitudes, this verse holds profound relevance. Responsible citizenship entails treating every member of society with dignity and respect, regardless of their differences. Ridiculing or belittling others based on their beliefs, appearance, or social standing contradicts the principles of civic sense and responsible conduct. The verse serves as a powerful warning to avoid from indulging in scornful behaviour, since it has the potential to destroy communal harmony and togetherness. Muslims may represent the spirit of responsible citizenship by fostering an atmosphere of mutual tolerance and understanding, in which each individual's contributions to society are accepted, acknowledged, and appreciated.

وَاعْبُدُوا اللَّهَ وَلَا تُشْرِكُوا بِهِ شَيْئًا وَبِالْوَالِدَيْنِ إِحْسَانًا وَبِذِي الْقُرْبَىٰ وَالْيَتَامَىٰ وَالْمَسْكِينِ وَالْجَارِ ذِي الْقُرْبَىٰ وَالْجَارِ الْجُنُبِ وَالصَّاحِبِ بِالْجَنبِ وَابْنِ السَّبِيلِ وَمَا

﴿36: سورة النساء: تَمَلَّكَتْ أَيْمَانُكُمْ ۚ إِنَّ اللَّهَ لَا يُحِبُّ مَنْ كَانَ مُخْتَالًا فَخُورًا﴾

'Worship Allah and associate nothing with Him, and to parents do good, and to relatives,

Orphans, the needy, the near neighbour, the neighbour farther away, the companion at your side, the traveler, and whom your right-hand possess. Indeed, Allah does not like those who are self-deluding and boastful.'

The Prophet (PBUH) said: "The best among you are those who have the best manners and character."³

This hadith highlights the significance of good manners and character in a society. It encourages individuals to cultivate positive attributes that contribute to the well-being and betterment of their community.

The Prophet (PBUH) said: "Whoever believes in Allah and the Last Day, let him speak good or remain silent."⁴

This hadith emphasizes the importance of being mindful of our words and the impact they can have on others. It encourages individuals to practice restraint and speak only when their words are beneficial, preventing harm to their community.

The Prophet (PBUH) said: "None of you truly believes until he loves for his brother what he loves for himself."⁵

This hadith highlights the concept of a sense of community and the importance of caring for others. It encourages individuals to have empathy, compassion, and consideration for fellow members of society, which helps in fostering a harmonious environment.

The Prophet (PBUH) said: "The believers, in their mutual love, mercy, and compassion, are like a single body; if one part is afflicted with pain, the whole body feels it, both in sleeplessness and fever."⁶

This hadith emphasizes the unity and connectivity of the Muslim community. It encourages individuals to be sensitive to the needs and concerns of others, promoting a society where people support and care for one another. These hadiths highlight the need for individuals to develop a strong civic sense, which includes having good manners, speaking kind words, showing empathy, and caring for others. By following these teachings, Muslims can contribute positively to society and create a more respectful and considerate environment.

The Prophet's (PBUH) treatment of neighbors:

The Prophet (PBUH) would prioritize the welfare of his neighbors and taught his followers to do the same. He emphasized the importance of maintaining good relations with neighbors, helping them in times of need, and refraining from causing them harm.

He said, "Jibril (Gabriel) kept advising me about (good) treatment of the neighbors until I thought that Allah would make them the heirs of the person."⁷

The Prophet's (PBUH) kindness towards children:

The Prophet (PBUH) would show great affection and kindness towards children. He would play with them, carry them, and even make time for their needs, regardless of their social status. His interactions with children reflected his understanding of their rights and the importance of nurturing their well-being.

The Prophet's (PBUH) respect for elders:

The Prophet (PBUH) would show great respect and honor towards elders. He would stand up when elders entered the room, listen attentively to their advice, seek their counsel, and treat them with kindness and compassion. This demonstrated his recognition of the wisdom and experience that elders possess and the value they bring to society. Quran says:

⁸ وبالوالدين احسانا.

“And treat your parents with mercy and love”

The Prophet's (PBUH) fair treatment of people:

Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) was known for his fair and just treatment of all individuals, regardless of their background, race, or social status. He upheld justice and equality, and his interactions with people reflected his commitment to treating everyone with respect and dignity.

9المسلم أخو المسلم لا يظلمه ولا يسلطه .

“The muslim is the brother of another muslim, he neither wrongs him nor does hand him over to one who does him wrong.”

10. المسلم من سلم المسلمون من لسانه ويده

“A muslim is he who from whose hand and tongue the Muslims are safe.”

11. ولا تجسسوا ولا يفتب بعضكم بعضا

“And do not spy or backbite each other”

12 انما المؤمنون اخوه فاصلحوا بين اخوكم .

“And believers are but brothers, so make settlement between your brothers”

13 ان جاءكم فاسق فبئروا قلوبهم ان يفتبونوا .

“O’ who have believed, if there comes to you a disobedient one with information, investigate ..”

Muslims are encouraged to be considerate of the feelings, rights, and dignity of all individuals, regardless of their background, religion, or social status.

2. Responsibility towards the Community: Muslims are taught to actively contribute to the well-being of their community. This includes participating in community development projects, supporting charitable causes, and helping those in need. Islam places a strong emphasis on caring for the poor, orphans, and the less fortunate. Some verses related to this are as follows:

14. وذروا ما بقي من الربوا

“Fear Allah and give up what remains (due to to you) of Interest.”

15. وليعفووا وليعظوا .

“And let them pardon and overlook.”

3. Upholding Justice and Fairness: The Quranic verses emphasizes the principle of treating others as we would wish to be treated by Allah Himself: ¹⁶“واحسن كما احسن الله اليك”-

17 فاحكم بين الناس بالحق ولا تتبع الهوى .

“So, Judge between the people in truth and do not follow (your own) desires.”

In the context of civic attitudes, this verse underscores the importance of embodying justice and fairness in our interactions with fellow citizens. Just as we expect Allah's kindness and justice, we are reminded to extend the same compassion and equitable treatment to others.

Upholding justice and fairness in civic matters means advocating for the rights of all, irrespective of their background or status, and striving to create an inclusive and just society. This hadith highlights the importance of being proactive in promoting good and preventing evil within society. Muslims are encouraged to actively participate in fostering positive change and promoting justice.

4. Honesty and Integrity: The Quranic verse from Surah Al-Baqarah advises believers to avoid engaging in transactions that involve usury, corruption money or dishonesty:

وتولوا للناس حسناً. وذروا ما بقي من الربوا¹⁸
 19 اكلون للسحت.

“Devourers of (what is) unlawful”

In the context of civic attitudes, this verse highlights the significance of honesty and integrity in financial dealings and commercial interactions within the society. By adhering to ethical principles and refraining from engaging in exploitative practices, Muslims can foster trust and transparency in financial matters, promoting a sense of responsibility and fairness in economic interactions.

5. Environmental consciousness: Islamic teachings promote the concept of environmental stewardship and emphasize the importance of taking care of the natural world. Muslims are encouraged to be mindful of their ecological footprint and to be responsible custodians of the Earth. The Quran says: “It is He who has appointed you vicegerent on the earth...”²⁰ “The servants of the Lord of Mercy are those who walk gently upon the earth”²¹ Islamic teachings oppose using resources in excess or in pursuit of an opulent lifestyle; extravagant excess by some typically deprives others of a basic standard of decent and secure living. Being steward on earth, Muslims are encouraged to be considerate and respectful towards the natural environment and the resources it provides. Muslims are instructed to look after the environment and not to damage it. The Prophet (PBUH) has prohibited cutting trees and destroying plants and forbade the abuse of natural sources. Moreover, He (PBUH) taught the importance of preserving the environment and avoiding wastefulness. He said, “The world is green and beautiful and Allah has appointed you as His stewards over it. He sees how you acquit yourselves.”²² By nurturing an awareness of the environment's importance and adopting sustainable practices, Muslims can demonstrate their sense of civic responsibility towards the preservation of nature for future generations. Encouraging sustainable practices and avoiding pollution can help address the rising trend of environmental degradation.

6. Active Participation in Governance: The Quranic verse from Surah Al-Hadid urges believers ‘to fear Allah and know that Allah is severe in penalty.’²³ Quran tells us:

”وان اكرم عند الله اتقم “²⁴

In the context of civic attitudes, this verse reminds Muslims of their responsibility to participate actively in governance and decision-making processes. By being mindful of Allah's commands and recognizing the importance of just governance, Muslims are encouraged to engage in civic affairs, vote responsibly, and hold leaders accountable for their actions. Active participation in governance demonstrates a sense of civic duty and commitment to the

betterment of society.

7. Obeying Laws and Regulations: Strengthen public behavior regulations and by-laws, increase law enforcement presence, and enforce strict laws to promote civic behavior and punish offenders. Implement fines for littering, spitting, and disruptive behavior. Strengthen the legal framework to ensure a safer environment.

25. الذين يوفون بعهد الله ولا يتخونون اليه

“Those who fulfill the covenant and do not break the contract.”

In the context of civic attitudes, this Quranic Ayat calls for adhering to laws and regulations that protect the welfare and safety of the community. By removing obstacles and harmful elements from public spaces, Muslims exemplify their sense of civic responsibility and commitment to the well-being of their fellow citizens. Obeying laws and regulations signify a willingness to cooperate and respect the social order for the greater good of society. The Prophet (PBUH) said, "Whosoever of you sees an evil, let him change it with his hand; and if he is not able to do so, then with his tongue; and if he is not able to do so, then with his heart – and that is the weakest of faith."²⁶

8. Social welfare and charity: The Hadith narrated by Abu Barzah Al-Aslami (R.A) provides profound guidance on social welfare and charity:

27. "قلبت يداي رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم على عمل لا أستغني به قال: اعزلن الأذى عن طريق المسلمين"

In this Hadith, the Prophet Muhammad (ﷺ) advises believers to remove harmful obstacles from the path of fellow Muslims. In the context of social welfare and charity, this Hadith calls for active engagement in charitable acts that alleviate the suffering of others. Embodying the essence of social welfare, Muslims are encouraged to extend a helping hand to those in distress, ensuring that their path towards prosperity is unobstructed by adversity. Quran Says to be kind and merciful to the people under debt and has commanded to write all contracts to avoid any mischiefs by the wrong-doers.

28. وان تصدقوا خير لكم. وان كان ذو عسرة فنظرة الى ميسرة ط

“And if someone is in hardship, then (let there be) postponement until (a time of) ease.”

29. اذا تبرأ منتم بدين الى اجل مسمى فاكتبوه

“O’ who have believed, when you contract a debt for a specified term, write it down”

The cultivation of Islamic civic sense assumes paramount importance for Muslims, as it fosters compassion, communal obligations, equitable justice, unwavering integrity, environmental stewardship, active participation in governance, and compliance with land regulations. By steadfastly upholding these foundational principles, Muslims fulfill their religious and societal duties, ultimately engendering cohesive and inclusive societies that yield collective benefits for all members. The Quranic verses and teachings of the Prophet (PBUH) resoundingly underscore the centrality of these guiding principles in Islamic conduct and governance.

Conclusion

To sum up everything we have learned and studied in this research, Islamic civic sense epitomizes responsible citizenship and benevolent engagement in Muslim societies. It entails compassion, empathy, and communal responsibility towards fellow human beings. Upholding justice, fairness, and integrity in financial matters ensures individual accountability and contributes to societal stability. Displaying forgiveness and inclusivity strengthens the fabric of the community, fostering mutual support.

Quranic verses and Hadiths underscore the vital role of social welfare and charity in Islam. Active participation in philanthropy and removing obstacles from others' paths exemplify the commitment to societal well-being. Environmental consciousness highlights the duty to safeguard natural resources for future generations, reflecting Islamic teachings on stewardship.

Islamic civic sense also embraces governance participation and adherence to laws. Responsible engagement in civic affairs and holding leaders accountable uphold good governance principles. By embodying these qualities, Muslims establish harmonious societies where empathy, compassion, and respect form the foundation of civic engagement. In essence, Islamic civic sense illuminates the path towards virtuous citizenship, communal well-being, and societal prosperity. Internalizing these principles, Muslims leave a legacy of compassionate stewardship, inspiring a world that values dignity, empathy, and social justice, reflecting the essence of Islam as a guiding beacon for humanity.

References / Endnotes

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 - ⁹ Sahih Bukhari, Kitab ul Mazalim, Hadith No. 2442.
 - ¹⁰ Sahih Bukhari, Kitab ul Iman, Hadith No.10 & Sahih Muslim
 - ¹¹ Quran Sura Al- Hujaraat Ayat No.12.
 - ¹² Quran Sura Al- Hujaraat Ayat No.10.
 - ¹³ Quran Sura Al- Hujaraat Ayat No.7.
 - ¹⁴ Quran Sura Baqarah Ayat No.278.
 - ¹⁵ Quran Sura Al-Noor Ayat No.22.
 - ¹⁶ Quran Sura Al-Qasas Ayat No.17.
 - ¹⁷ Quran Sura Saad Ayat No.26.
 - ¹⁸ Qura'an, Sura Nisa'a Ayat No.36 & Baqarah Ayat No.278.
 - ¹⁹ Quran Sura Maidah Ayat No.42.
 - ²⁰ Quran, Sura Al-Inaam, Ayat No.165.
 - ²¹ Quran, Sura A-Furqan, Ayat No.63.
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²² Sahih Muslim

²³ Quran, Sura Al-Hadid, Ayat No. 25.

²⁴ Quran Sura Al- Hujaraat Ayat No.13.

²⁵ Quran Sura Ra'ad Ayat No.20.

²⁶ Sahih Muslim, Baab ul Iman, Names and Rulings, Faith increases or decreases.

²⁷ Sunan e Ibne Maaja, Hadith No.3681.

²⁸ Quran Sura Baqarah Ayat No.280.

²⁹ Quran Sura Baqarah Ayat No.282

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